

A Study on Customer Preference towards Aavin Milk Products with Special Reference to Nilgiri District

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ABSTRACT

India is the world's largest dairy producer Indian dairy sector has grown substantively over the years. Dairy products demand in India has increased dramatically in both rural and urban sectors. However, as a larger population is migrating from rural areas to cities. Thus, creates greater demand for dairy products. Tamil Nadu state is the one of the ten largest milk producing states in India. In the state, major milk contributor is aavin, a Tamil Nadu- based milk producer's union, procures milk, processes it and sells milk and milk products to customers. This paper analyses customer preference over the aavin with special reference to the nilgiri district. The aim of the study is reveal customer preference over aavin milk products based on their age, education qualification, and monthly income of the customer's family. It also depicts level of satisfaction about the product using simple percentage analyses.

Key Words: aavin, customer, dairy products

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INTRODUCTION:

A study on customer's preference of milk and milk products of Aavin with reference to Nilgiri district is undertaken or assessing the expectations of the customers towards milk and milk products which will in turn help to take appropriate action by management for removing the short falls. To interrogate customer's area -sampling system was adopted, since the population is undefined so 50 customers was interrogated to elicit the information, which are analyzed, interpreted and placed under with comments, charts and findings. The idea that customers prefer one product or one service over another is not new. The ability to identify and measure the element of such preference decisions with any accuracy and reliability has only recently become available. Research into this area of consumer behavior has brought understanding to some of the major issues with standard customer satisfaction research. Most importantly, we have come to realize that high customer satisfaction does not assure continued customer preference, satisfaction research over the past fifteen years demonstrates that high satisfaction scores, while a measure of organization performance on a set important criteria, do not adequately explain the composition of preference formation and therefore serve as insufficient predictors of sustained preference or what is normally referred to as customer's loyalty.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Boopathi.B (1999) India is the world's largest dairy producer. Indian Dairy sector has grown substantively over the years. Dairy products demand in India has increased dramatically in both rural and urban sectors. However, as a larger population is migrating from rural areas to cities. Thus, creates greater demand for dairy products. Tamil Nadu state is the one of the ten largest milk producing states in India. In the state, major milk contributor is Aavin, a Tamil Nadu-based milk producer's union, procures milk, processes it and sells milk and milk products to consumers. This paper analyses consumer perception over the Aavin special reference to the Pollachi Taluk of Tamil Nadu State. The aim of the study is reveal consumer perception over Aavin milk products based on their age, educational qualification and monthly income of the consumers' family. It also depicts level of satisfaction about the product using chi-square test.

According to James c.cox (2000) in the economic journal, consumer economics traditionally operates on the hypothesis that consumers seeks the most utility, or satisfaction that they can buy consumer preference involves the ranking of goods and services according to how much benefit they afford. The study of consumer preference employs assumptions about consumer behavior and how they decide preference. A Consumer preference explains how a consumer ranks a collection of goods or services or

services or prefers one collection over another this definition assumes that consumers rank goods or services by the amount of satisfaction, or utility, afforded. Consumer preference theory does not take the consumers income, good or services price, or the consumer's ability to purchase the product or service.

John McKean (2001) in an excellent book, customers are people – The human touch think of the organization – customers' interaction as a series of cascading touch points. Those touch points comprise the customer's environment and it is through interacting with the environment that customer's preference is formed. The idea that customers prefer one product or one service over another is not new. The ability to identify and measure the element of such preference decisions with any accuracy and reliability has only recently become available. Research into this area of consumer behavior has brought understanding to some of the major issues with standard customer satisfaction research. Most importantly, we have come to realize that high customer satisfaction does not assure continued customer preference, satisfaction research over the past fifteen years demonstrates that high satisfaction scores, while a measure of organization performance on a set important criteria, do not adequately explain the composition of preference formation and therefore often serve as insufficient predictors of sustained preference or what is normally referred to as customer's loyalty.

Boopathi. C (2002) the project entitled "An Overview of consumer behavior of Aavin milk with reference to Erode District" is carried out with an objective to determine the customer behavior towards Aavin milk products and to find out the customer mentality towards using the service. The research mainly focuses on the factors like quality, consumer preference, price, service, attitudes and experience of consumers. In this study, data are collected from the consumers through questionnaire (interview schedule). 100 samples are selected using convenience sampling. Using the interview schedule prepared, the 100 consumers are interviewed personally and their opinion was collected. Secondary data was collected from related websites, books. The collected data is analyzed using simple percentage and chi-square. As per the findings, suggestions are given to the company to take initiation to fulfill the consumer needs.

Huang (2003) in his online study of websites, found that level of attention in consumers is most linked to utilitarian design while both control and interest are linked to hedonic performance measures.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Aavin, Perambalur union plays a vital role in marketing. The success of the Milk and dairy products depends not only, the marketing but also the customers' behavior pattern towards their product. To have better marketing the union needs a maximum inspiration from the customer side. If marketing is done without the execution of customer, it cannot run success fully for a long period of time. So an analytical study is conducted based on customer satisfied with regard to market the milk and it by product.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research in common parlance refers to a search for knowledge. One can also define research as a scientific and systemic search for pertinent information on a specific topic. In fact, research is an art of scientific investigation.

Data becomes information only when a proper methodology is adopted. Thus we say methodology is a tool, which process the data to reliable information. The present chapter attempt to highlight the research methodology adopted in this project.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To understand the loyalty of the customers towards the milk products of Aavin.
2. To identify customer's expectation towards the milk products of Aavin
3. To identify the performance of Aavin and its products.
4. To understand customer's behavior in choosing the milk and other milk products of Aavin.

DATA COLLECTION METHOD

The data is collected both from primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected from customers through questionnaire and secondary data was collected from previous records. Articles, journals, magazines, publications and details given by the company.

➤ **Primary data and collection method**

Primary data is the data that is collected for the time by the researcher. The primary data are collected with the specific set of objective to assess the current status any variable studied. Primary data is useful for only the particular period.

➤ **Questionnaire**

In this study, a structured questionnaire was used by the research for collecting data. The questionnaire contains around twenty four questions pertaining to different aspects of customer preference of Aavin milk products.

➤ **Secondary data and collection method**

Secondary data is collected from company records, company websites and documents. Sampling Method and Sample size.

TOOLS USED FOR STUDY

- Simple percentage analysis

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

Percentage refers to a special kind of ratio. Percentage is used for making comparison about two or more series of data.

FORMULA

$$\frac{\text{Number of respondents}}{\text{Total number of respondents}} * 100$$

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATIONS

The data collected through various sources have been analyzed in the following pages.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

TABLE-1 SHOWING CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON GENDER

S. NO	Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Male	15	30
2	Female	35	70
Total		50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION

From the Table 1 shows interpretation that 30% of the respondents are male and 70% of the respondents are female.

TABLE-2 SHOWING CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON AGE

S. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 18 years	03	06
2	18-30 years	30	60
3	30-50 years	13	26
4	More than 50 years	04	08
Total		50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION

From the Table 2 we interpretation that 6% of ages of the respondents are less than 18 years, 60% of ages of the respondents are 18-30 years, 26% of ages of respondents are 30-50 years, and 8% of ages of the respondents are more than 50 years.

TABLE-3 CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON OCCUPATION

S. no	Particulars	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Professional	18	36
2	Housewife	21	42
3	Students	04	8
4	Business man	03	6
5	Others	04	8
Total		50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION

From the Table 3 we interpretation that 36% of the respondents are housewife, 8% of the respondents are students, 6% of the respondents are businessman and 8% of the respondents are in other occupation

TABLE-4 CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON MONTHLY INCOME

S. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 5000	1	02
2	5000-10000	7	14
3	10000-15000	14	28
4	More than 15000	28	56
Total		50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION

From the Table 4 we interpretation that 2% of the respondents get monthly income less than 5000, 14% of the respondents get 5000-10000, 28% of the respondents get 10000-15000 and 56% of the respondents get more than 15000.

TABLE-5 CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON THE NUMBER OF FAMILY MEMBERS

S. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	3 or less than 3	10	20
2	3-4	15	30
3	4-5	10	20
4	More than 5	10	30
Total		50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION

From the Table 5 we interpretation that 20% of the respondents are 3 or less than 3 members in the family, 30% of the respondents are 3-4 members in the family, 20% of the respondents are 4-5 members in the family and 30% of the respondents are more than 5 members in the family.

TABLE-6 CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON THE TYPE OF BRAND THEY USE

S. No	Particulars	No of respondents	Percentage
1	Aavin	30	60
2	Aroyaka	10	20
3	Sakthi	05	10
4	Others	05	10
	Total	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION

From the Table 6 interpretation that 60% of the respondents are prefer AAVIN milk,20% of the respondents are prefer aroky,10% of the respondents are prefer Sakthi Milk and 10% respondents are prefer other brand milk.

TABLE-7 CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON THEIR CONSUMPTION OF MILK PER DAY

S. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than half	02	4
2	Half liter	20	40
3	1 liter	18	36
4	More than 1 liter	10	20
	Total	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION

From the Table 7 we interpretation that 4% of the respondents consumes less than half a liter per day, 40% of the respondents consumes half a liter per day, 36% of the respondents consumes 1 liter per day and 20% of the respondents consumes more than 1 liter per day.

TABLE-8 CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON DURATION OF THE CONSUMPTION OF AAVIN MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS

S. No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less than 1 year	5	10
2	1-2 year	11	22
3	2-5 year	14	28
4	More than 5 years	20	40
	Total	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION

From the Table 8 we interpretation that 10% of the respondents consume Aavin milk less than 1 years, 22% of the respondent's consume 1-2 years, 28% of the respondents consume 2-5 years and 40% of the respondents consume more than 5 years.

TABLE-9 CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON AWARENESS OF AAVIN MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS

S. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Media	03	06
2	Word of mouth	17	34
3	Banners	10	20
4	Leaflets	10	20
5	Others	10	20
	Total	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION

From the Table 9 we interpretation that 6% of the respondents were aware of the Aavin products through media,34% of the respondents were aware through word of mouth, 20% of the respondents were aware through banners, 20% of the respondents were aware through leaflets and 20% of the respondents were aware through others.

TABLE-10 CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON THEIR ATTITUDE TOWARDS AVAVIN MILK AND PRODUCTS

S. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	30	60
2	No	20	40
	Total	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION

From the Table 10 we interpretation that 60% of the respondents are think Aavin milk and milk products are easily available and 40% of the respondents are think Aavin milk and milk products are not easily available.

TABLE-11 CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON THEIR ATTITUDE TOWARDS THE ADVERTISEMENT OF MILK PRODUCTS

S. No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	T.V	28	56
2	Radio	06	12
3	Newspaper	08	16
4	Magazine	08	16
	Total	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION

From the Table 11 we interpretation that 56% of the respondents are say that advertisement should be given in TV, 12% of the respondents are say that advertisement should be given in Radio,16% of the respondents are say that advertisements should be given in Newspaper and 16% of respondents are say that the advertisement should be given in magazine.

TABLE-12 CLASSIFICATION OF RESPONDENTS BASED ON THEIR PREFERENCE OVER MILK PRODUCT

S. No	Particulars	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Butter	15	30
2	Ice cream	05	10
3	Curd	26	32
4	Milk Sweet	04	08
	Total	50	100

Source: primary data

INTERPRETATION

From Table 12 we interpretation that 30% of respondents are prefer butter,10% of the respondents are prefer ice cream, 32% of the respondents are prefer curd,08% of the respondents are prefer milk sweet and 10% of the respondents are prefer other ite.

FINDINGS SUGGESTION AND CONCLUSION

FINDINGS

- Maximum 70% of respondents are female
- Maximum 60% of the respondents are between 18-30
- Maximum 42% of the respondents are house wife
- Maximum 56% of the respondent’s monthly income is more than 15000.
- Maximum 30% of respondents are more than 5 members in a family.
- Maximum 60% of the respondents preferred only Aavin brand
- Maximum 40% of the respondents are consuming ½ liter milk per day
- Maximum 40% of the respondents are more than five years old who consumes Aavin milk
- Maximum 34% of the respondents are well aware of Aavin milk products
- 60% of the respondents are using Aavin milk.
- Maximum 56% of the respondents use T.V as their media as suitable advertisement
- Maximum 32% of the respondents prefer Aavin curd

SUGGESTIONS

- The price of Aavin milk and milk products should be reduced.
- The number of Aavin booth should be increased to satisfy more number of customers.
- More number of retail outlets should be opened in rural areas to attract more customers.
- Effective marketing and campaigning should be done to yield more number of customers.
- The milk packets is 250ml should be made available to the customers for their convenience.
- More awareness should be given to the customers about the varieties of Aavin milk products.
- The customer care center of Aavin should be effective and efficient in handling customer’s queries and complaints.
- The preservation should be improved to avoid quick spoilage of milk products.
- It suggests that the quality of Aavin milk products should be improved.

CONCLUSION

From the survey conducted it is observed that Aavin milk and milk products has a good market share. From the study conducted the following conclusions can be drawn. In order to convert the dreams into reality and for turning liabilities into assets one must have to meet the needs of the customers. The factors considered by the customer before purchasing milk are freshness, taste thickness and easy availability. Finally I conclude that, majority of the customers are satisfied with Aavin milk and milk products because of its good quality, reputation, easy availabilities. Some customers are not satisfied with the Aavin milk and products because of high price, lack of dealer service, spoilage and low shelf life etc. therefore, if slight modification in the marketing programmers such as dealers and outlets, promotion programmers, product lines etc., definitely company can be as a monopoly and strong market leader. Aavin has also to take care of competitors and more importantly its customers before making any move.

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